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**Oxidation of Monochloroacetic Acid by Potassium
Permanganate at Wave-lengths 366 $\mu\mu$ and
436 $\mu\mu$ with Uranyl Salt as Photosensitiser.**

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In a previous paper Ghosh, Narayanmurti and Ray (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1935, **B 29**, 236) published the results of an investigation on the oxidation of mandelic acid by methylene blue with uranyl nitrate as photosensitiser. Mandelic acid is easily oxidised into phenylpyruvic acid which decomposes to produce benzaldehyde. It was found that almost every collision between the excited uranyl ion with mandelic acid results in this oxidative change. In this paper, the photo-oxidation of monochloroacetic acid, which is a much stabler compound, has been studied using potassium permanganate as the oxidant.

The experimental arrangement is the same as described in the previous paper, the source of light being a point-source quartz mercury lamp from which parallel beams of light were obtained by using quartz lenses. The reaction cells were made of fused quartz plates sealed into one another without cement and had the dimensions 1.8 cm. $\times$ 1.8 cm. $\times$ 0.5 cm. The following filters were used for monochromatism :

436 $\mu\mu$ —Schott and Gen Blue filter (U.4) + 2 cm. of 2% copper sulphate solution in water.

366 $\mu\mu$ —Chance Bros. U. V. filter (1 mm.) + 2 cm. of 2% copper sulphate solution in water.

The liquid filters were contained in quartz cells and were placed between the lens and the reaction cell.

The course of reaction was followed by observing the change in concentration of potassium permanganate. The concentration in the reaction cell was measured by observing the absorption of light at

540 $\mu\mu$ with the aid of a König-Marten spectrophotometer. At the concentration used, the uranyl sulphate in the mixture does not perceptibly affect the spectrophotometric readings. On plotting the values of $\log \tan \theta$, (θ being the spectrophotometric angle) against the corresponding concentration of KMnO_4 , a straight line was obtained. In any experiment, therefore, the observed value of θ at any moment becomes a measure of the concentration of KMnO_4 at that moment.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Rideal and Norrish (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, **A**, 103, 342) have shown that ultraviolet light of wave-length 366 $\mu\mu$ as also visible light, have no action on a solution of potassium permanganate.

No change in concentration of potassium permanganate was also observed when (i) a mixture of 0.0005M- KMnO_4 and 0.1M-monochloroacetic acid was illuminated by light of $\lambda=366 \mu\mu$, or (ii) when a mixture of 0.1 M-uranyl sulphate and 0.0005 M- KMnO_4 was similarly exposed.

Also, no reaction was found to take place when a mixture of potassium permanganate, monochloroacetic acid and uranyl sulphate was kept in the dark.

When, however, the mixture was exposed to radiation 366 $\mu\mu$, there was gradual decolourisation of potassium permanganate showing that reaction was taking place. The reaction is purely zero-molecular with respect to KMnO_4 .

The following is a typical example.

$\Delta x/\Delta t$ gives the number of g. molecules of KMnO_4 reacting per unit area of the solution of 5 mm. thickness per sec. There is no induction period.

TABLE Ia.

KMnO_4 conc. = 0.00051M. CH_2ClCOOH conc. = 0.1M. UO_2SO_4 conc. = 0.1M. H_2SO_4 conc. = 2.5N.

Temp. = 30°. Incident intensity = 2650 ergs/sec. cm^2 . at 366 $\mu\mu$.

Time.	Spectrophoto reading.	Conc. of KMnO_4 .	$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \times 10^{11}$.
0 sec.	65.5	$5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$	
3600	61.5	3.9×10^{-4}	1.5
4860	60.5	3.6×10^{-4}	1.4
7200	57.5	2.8×10^{-4}	1.5
8580	56.0	2.4×10^{-4}	1.5
		Mean	1.5

TABLE Ib.

KMnO₄ conc. = 0.00042M. CH₂ClCOOH conc. = 0.03M.
 UO₂SO₄ conc. = 0.1M. H₂SO₄ conc. = 3N.
 Temp. = 30°. Incident intensity = 930 ergs/sec. cm² at 436 μμ.

Time.	Spectrophoto reading.	Conc. of KMnO ₄ .	$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \times 10^{11}$.
0 sec.	64.0	$4.5 \times 10^{-4}M$	
4740	62.7	4.2×10^{-4}	0.327
8760	61.7	3.9×10^{-4}	0.34
			Mean 0.33

The radiation absorbed by uranyl sulphate in the mixture which is the only photo-active material in the system was calculated by the approximate formula,

$$I_{\text{abs}} = I_0 \left[1 - e^{-\epsilon_1 c_1 d - \epsilon_2 c_2 d} \right] \frac{\epsilon_1 c_1}{\epsilon_1 c_1 + \epsilon_2 c_2} \quad \dots (i)$$

where I_0 = intensity of incident radiation, measured by Moll galvanometer and thermopile; ϵ_1 = enhanced extinction coefficient of uranyl sulphate in presence of monochloroacetic acid; c_1 = concentration of uranyl sulphate; ϵ_2 = extinction coefficient of potassium permanganate and c_2 = concentration of potassium permanganate.

The extinction coefficients were measured by means of a Moll galvanometer and thermopile, calibrated against a standard Hefner lamp tested by the Bureau of Standards. The intensities of light incident and transmitted through the solution were measured and the molar extinction coefficient determined from the equation

$$\epsilon = \frac{\log_e I_0 - \log_e I_t}{c.d.}$$

where c is the concentration of the solution and d , the thickness.

Table II gives the extinction coefficient of potassium permanganate in sulphuric acid solution at wave-length 366 μμ.

TABLE II.

KMnO ₄ conc.	<i>d</i> .	<i>I</i> ₀ .	Radiation transmitted	
			<i>I</i> _t .	ϵ .
$6.8 \times 10^{-4}M$	0.5 cm.	3080 ergs	1600 ergs	1900
2.3×10^{-4}	0.5	3080	2450	2020
3.0×10^{-4}	1.0	2100	1130	2050
				Mean 2000

This value of the extinction coefficient of KMnO₄ was verified by taking photographs of absorption spectra of a $4.7 \times 10^{-4}M$ solution of KMnO₄ by means of a Hilger spectrograph with a rotating sector. From the absorption curve the value of $1/d \log_{10} I_0/I_t$ at wavelength $366 \mu\mu$ was found to be 0.38, so that

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{c \cdot d} \log I_0/I_t = 1860$$

At $436 \mu\mu$, $\frac{1}{d} \log_{10} I_0/I_t = 0.045$. $\therefore \epsilon = 220$.

The experimental results are recorded below.

TABLE III.

Composition of solution.	Extinction coefficient ϵ at	
	$\lambda = 436 \mu\mu$.	$\lambda = 366 \mu\mu$.
KMnO ₄	220	2000
UO ₂ SO ₄ in presence of excess of CH ₂ CICOOH	6.5	10

It will be noted that a zero-molecular velocity constant, that is, a constant velocity of reaction as indicated by the rate of disappearance of KMnO₄ must lead to the conclusion that the radiant energy absorbed by the uranyl ion in solution is independent of the relative concentration of KMnO₄ and its reduction product; that is in equation (i), $\epsilon_2 c_2$ is practically constant, whether it be due to KMnO₄ or a mixture of KMnO₄ and its reduction product.

This was verified in the following way. To a definite concentration of KMnO₄ in sulphuric acid, different concentrations of oxalic

acid were added, there being excess of permanganate in each case, and the absorption of the solutions were measured. The radiation $366 \mu\mu$ absorbed were found to be practically the same in all cases.

TABLE IV.

Comp. of soln. (5 mm. thick)	Conc. of KMnO_4 in the mixture.	Incident intensity.	Radiation absorbed.
$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2 \text{ c.c. } 0.00245M\text{-KMnO}_4 \\ 5 \text{ c.c. } 5N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4 \\ 2 \text{ c.c. water} \end{array} \right.$	$5.4 \times 10^{-4} M$	3000 ergs	1140 ergs
$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2 \text{ c.c. } 0.00245M\text{-KMnO}_4 \\ 5 \text{ c.c. } 5N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4 \\ 0.5 \text{ c.c. } 0.01N\text{-oxalic acid} \\ 1.5 \text{ c.c. water} \end{array} \right.$	4.25×10^{-4}	Do.	1120
$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2 \text{ c.c. } 0.00245 M \text{ KMnO}_4 \\ 5 \text{ c.c. } 5N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4 \\ 1 \text{ c.c. } 0.01 N\text{-oxalic acid} \\ 1 \text{ c.c. water} \end{array} \right.$	3.2×10^{-4}	Do.	1110

This result was confirmed by taking photographs of absorption spectra of the following solutions by means of a Hilger spectrograph with a rotating sector.

TABLE V.

Composition of solution.	Conc. of KMnO_4 in the mixture.
$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 10 \text{ c.c. } 0.00235M\text{-KMnO}_4 \\ 20 \text{ c.c. } 7 N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4 \\ 20 \text{ c.c. water} \end{array} \right.$	$4.7 \times 10^{-4} M$
$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 10 \text{ c.c. } 0.00235 M\text{-KMnO}_4 \\ 20 \text{ c.c. } 7 N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4 \\ 2 \text{ c.c. } 0.01 N\text{-oxalic acid} \\ 18 \text{ c.c. water} \end{array} \right.$	3.9×10^{-4}
$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 10 \text{ c.c. } 0.00235 M\text{-KMnO}_4 \\ 20 \text{ c.c. } 7 N \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4 \\ 5 \text{ c.c. } 0.01 N\text{-oxalic acid} \\ 15 \text{ c.c. water} \end{array} \right.$	2.65×10^{-4}

The three absorption curves of the solutions were found to be practically identical, which confirms the view that in reaction of KMnO_4 with monochloroacetic acid, the value of ϵ_{2c_2} in equation (i) remains practically constant.

Effect of Conc. of Monochloroacetic Acid on the Velocity of Reaction.—The velocity of reaction was found to be dependent on the conc. of monochloroacetic acid, decreasing with decrease in concentra-

tion of the acceptor. The reciprocal of the velocity plotted against the reciprocal of concentration of CH_2ClCOOH gave a straight line.

TABLE VI.

KMnO_4 conc. = $4.2 \times 10^{-4} M$. UO_2SO_4 conc. = $0.087 M$. H_2SO_4 conc. = $3 N$. Temp. = 29° . $\lambda = 436 \mu\mu$.

$I_0 = 1030$ ergs. Energy absorbed by $\text{UO}_2\text{SO}_4 = 250$ ergs. No. of quanta absorbed/sec. $\text{cm}^2 = 5.5 \times 10^{13}$.

Conc. of CH_2ClCOOH	... $0.033 M$	$0.05 M$	$0.1 M$	$0.2 M$
$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \times 10^{11}$	... 0.34	0.43	0.57	0.66
Quantum efficiency	... 0.038	0.048	0.063	0.073

The significance of these results will be discussed later.

Influence of the Energy of Radiation absorbed by the Photosensitiser and the Concentration of the Photosensitiser on the Velocity of Reaction.—The velocity of reaction increases with increase in concentration of the sensitiser UO_2SO_4 , until at higher concentration it becomes practically constant. In the fifth column of Table VII are given the calculated velocity of reaction according to the equation

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} = K_0 \frac{I_{\text{abs}} \text{ by } \text{U}\ddot{\text{O}}_2}{1 + 9.08[\text{U}\ddot{\text{O}}_2]} \quad \dots \text{ (ii)}$$

TABLE VII.

CH_2ClCOOH conc. = $0.1 M$. KMnO_4 conc. = $4.2 \times 10^{-4} M$. H_2SO_4 conc. = $3 N$. Temp. = 29° .

(a) Incident intensity = 1030 ergs/sec. cm^2 . at $\lambda = 436 \mu\mu$.

1. Conc. of UO_2SO_4 .	2. Radiation absorbed by UO_2SO_4	3. No. of quanta absorbed/sec. cm^2 .	4. $\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \times 10^{11}$ Obs.	5. Vel. calc. from eq. (ii).	6. Quantum efficiency.
$0.0218 M$	70 ergs	1.57×10^{13}	0.26	0.24	0.10
0.0436	134	3.0×10^{13}	0.38	0.40	0.077
0.0653	193	4.3×10^{13}	0.47	0.49 taking K_0 $= 4.1 \times 10^{-3}$	0.067
0.0871	249	5.5×10^{13}	0.57	0.57	0.063
0.1511	373	8.3×10^{13}	0.68	0.65	0.05
0.2267	526	11.9×10^{13}	0.70	0.70	0.036

TABLE VII (contd.)

 (b) Incident intensity = 3360 ergs/sec. cm². at $\lambda = 366\mu\mu$.

1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.
0.0218 M	283 ergs	0.53×10^{11}	1.02	0.94	0.12
0.0436	540	1.0×10^{11}	1.47	1.50	0.09
0.0653	770	1.4×10^{11}	1.89	1.88 taking $K_0 = 3.9 \times 10^{-3}$	0.082
0.0871	975	1.8×10^{11}	2.05	2.12	0.07
0.1511	1490	2.8×10^{11}	2.29	2.40	0.05
0.2267	1925	3.6×10^{11}	2.45	2.45	0.042

Velocity Constant and Intensity of Incident Light.—The intensity of incident radiation was varied by using quartz lenses of different focal lengths.

TABLE VIII.

 KMnO_4 conc. = 5.1×10^{-4} M. CH_2ClCOOH conc. = 0.1 M.

 H_2SO_4 conc. = 2.6 N. Temp. = 29°.

Conc. of UO_2SO_4	I_0 at $366\mu\mu$.	$K_0 \times 10^{11}$.	I'_0 at $366\mu\mu$.	$K'_0 \times 10^{11}$.	$\frac{I_0}{I'_0}$	$\frac{K_0}{K'_0}$
0.05 M	4190 ergs	1.98	2650 ergs	1.21	1.58	1.63
0.1	4190	2.33	2650	1.49	1.58	1.56

It will thus be seen that with other experimental factors remaining the same, the velocity of reaction is directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation.

Temperature Coefficient.

TABLE IX.

 KMnO_4 conc. = 5.2×10^{-4} M. CH_2ClCOOH conc. = 0.08 M.

 H_2SO_4 conc. = 2.8 N. $I_0 = 2870$ ergs/sec. cm². at $\lambda = 366\mu\mu$.

Temp.	Conc. of UO_2SO_4 .	$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \times 10^{11}$.	Temp. coeff. (per 10°).
30°	0.067 M	1.23	1.02
40°	"	1.26	
30°	0.0335	1.01	1.04
40°	"	1.05	

Temperature coefficient is thus approximately equal to unity.

DISCUSSION.

From the experimental results it follows that any mechanism of reaction that may be proposed for this photo-sensitised oxidation, should be in a position to explain the following facts :

(i) The velocity of reaction is zero-molecular with respect to potassium permanganate.

(ii) With other factors remaining constant, the reciprocal of the velocity of reaction plotted against the reciprocal of the concentration of monochloroacetic acid, is a straight line.

(iii) The velocity of reaction is directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation.

(iv) The velocity of reaction is influenced by change in concentration of uranyl sulphate, according to the following equation

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} = K_0 \cdot \frac{I_{\text{abs}} \text{ by } \text{UO}_2^{\ddot{}}}{1 + 9.08[\text{UO}_2^{\ddot{}}]}$$

when concentration of monochloroacetic acid is 0.1M.

All these characteristics can be explained if we assume the following mechanism of reaction.

Equating the stationary concentration of $\text{UO}_2^{\ddot{*}}$, we get for the velocity of oxidation of monochloroacetic acid the following equation :—

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} = \frac{I_{\text{abs}} \text{ by } \text{UO}_2^{\ddot{}}}{Nh\nu} \cdot \frac{k_4[\text{Mc}]}{k_2 + k_3[\text{UO}_2^{\ddot{}}] + k_4[\text{Mc}]} \quad \dots (a)$$

where [Mc] is the conc. of monochloroacetic acid.

The fluorescence of uranyl salts has been studied by Wawilow (*Z. Physik*, 1928, 50, 56). Reactions (1), (2) and (3) above, give the

mechanism of fluorescent radiation in pure aqueous solution. The intensity of fluorescent radiation was found by Wawilow to be quantitatively expressed by the equation

$$\frac{I}{L} = \frac{I}{L_0} + 3.45 \times 10^2 C \quad \dots (b)$$

where C is the concentration of uranyl salt in g./c.c., L is the observed fluorescent intensity and L_0 is the limiting value of the fluorescent intensity when the conc. of uranyl salt is infinitely small, that is, reaction (3) does not take place. Under this limiting condition, every $U\ddot{O}_2$ -ion excited by absorbed radiation re-emits the same as fluorescent radiation. We may write equation (b) in the form

$$L = \frac{L_0}{1 + 3.45 \times 10^2 C} \quad \dots (c)$$

$$\text{or } L = \frac{L_0}{1 + 2.84 \times 10^2 C}$$

Since L_0 was found to have the experimental value 0.82.

$$\text{If } C \text{ be expressed in g. mol/litre, } L = \frac{L_0}{1 + 99[U\ddot{O}_2]} \quad \dots (d)$$

Now considering reactions (1), (2) and (3) above, we get

$$\begin{aligned} L &= \frac{I_{\text{abs by } U\ddot{O}_2}}{Nh\nu} \cdot \frac{k_2}{k_2 + k_3 [U\ddot{O}_2]} \\ &= \frac{I_{\text{abs}}}{Nh\nu} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + k_3/k_2 [U\ddot{O}_2]} \end{aligned}$$

From Wawilow's experimental data on the emission of fluorescent radiation by uranyl salts, it is, therefore, possible to find out the value of k_3/k_2 , which from equation (d) is equal to 99

$$\text{or } k_3 = 99 k_2.$$

The values of k_3 and k_4 , which depend upon the kinetic collision, have practically the same magnitude, if we assume that each collision between the excited ion of $U\ddot{O}_2$ and a normal $U\ddot{O}_2$ -ion or a monochloroacetic acid molecule leads to chemical transformation.

$$\text{Hence } k_4 = k_3 = 99 k_2.$$

Equation (a) may, therefore, be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} &= \frac{I_{\text{abs}} \text{ by } \text{U}\ddot{\text{O}}_2}{Nh\nu} \cdot \frac{k_4 [\text{Mc}]}{k_2 + k_4 [\text{Mc}]} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \frac{k_1 [\text{U}\ddot{\text{O}}_2]}{k_2 + k_4 [\text{Mc}]}} \\ &= \frac{I_{\text{abs}}}{Nh\nu} \cdot \frac{k_4 [\text{Mc}]}{k_2 + k_4 [\text{Mc}]} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + 9\cdot08 [\text{U}\ddot{\text{O}}_2]} \dots (e) \\ &\quad (\text{where the conc. of } \text{CH}_2\text{ClCOOH} \text{ is } 0\cdot1 \text{ M}). \\ &= \frac{k}{Nh\nu} \cdot \frac{I_{\text{abs}}}{1 + 9\cdot08 [\text{U}\ddot{\text{O}}_2]} \text{ where } K = \frac{k_4 [\text{Mc}]}{k_2 + k_1 [\text{Mc}]} \end{aligned}$$

The values of K_0 recorded in Table VIII are, therefore, identical with $k/Nh\nu$. Again from equation (a)

$$\frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} = \frac{Nh\nu}{I_{\text{abs}}} + \frac{Nh\nu}{I_{\text{abs}}} \cdot \frac{k_2 + k_3 [\text{U}\ddot{\text{O}}_2]}{k_4 [\text{Mc}]}$$

Thus the values of $[\text{U}\ddot{\text{O}}_2]$ and I_{abs} remaining constant, the reciprocal of velocity, $\Delta t/\Delta x$, plotted against the reciprocal of concentration of monochloroacetic acid should give a straight line and this has been found to be the case.

Quantum Efficiency.—Equation (e) indicates that the quantum efficiency of the oxidation of monochloroacetic acid, which is equal to $\Delta x/\Delta t \cdot I_{\text{abs}}/Nh\nu$ will be dependent on the concentration of monochloroacetic acid. For large concentration of the acid, the value of $k_4 [\text{Mc}]/k_2 + k_4 [\text{Mc}]$ becomes practically equal to unity, so that equation (e) reduces to the form

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} = \frac{I_{\text{abs}}}{Nh\nu} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + 9\cdot08 [\text{U}\ddot{\text{O}}_2]}$$

The quantum efficiency gradually falls off with increasing concentration of uranyl sulphate, as more and more of the light absorbed is dissipated by collision of the second kind.